

Hello dear.

I wrote an article on the fundamental principles of natural selection, survival, and adaptation. So far, I have not received any comments, criticisms, or suggestions from biologists and scientists regarding this article .

Do not be discouraged by the content and many pages of this article. I have been working on this for several years. So far, I have edited this article more than 30 or 40 times. I know this article still needs editing. I am working on editing and summarizing the article.

I am sending you a video of about 17 minutes. In this video, I explain the basic principles of natural selection adaptation and survival. I show that adaptation and survival are driven by natural selection based on these basic principles.

Sorry if the video is a little long. The time of the video is long because I tried to show in this video that these fundamental principles can explain and analyze many topics, materials, and concepts related to biology, evolution, natural selection, adaptation, and survival better than before. I request you to watch this movie till the end.

Video link:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11269588>

I am not sure if these fundamental principles are correct or not? Have other scientists already published papers on these fundamental principles that I don't know about? If you know, let me know by email.

I want to know if my view about these fundamental principles is correct or not. Is adaptation and survival by natural selection based on these fundamental principles? Is this a new perspective? Is this hypothesis new? Am I wrong and these fundamental principles are not correct?

So far I have not received any comments from biologists and scientists.

I request you to read this article and send me your comments, suggestions, and criticisms by email.

If you know a biologist or scientist who would be interested and expert in reviewing this article, please send them the link to the article.

Yours sincerely

Mohammad Yousef Arbab

The fundamental principles of natural selection, survival and adaptation: What characteristics does natural selection consider during adaptation, survival, and reproduction?

*Mohammad Yousef Arbab; Iranian; Sistan and Baluchistan Province; Saravan City.

Mohammad.yousef.arbab@gmail.com

Abstract

Natural selection was first proposed by Mr. Darwin and Mr. Wallace. Natural selection is a process that, during successive generations, leads to the creation of hereditary traits that increase the probability of survival and reproduction of living organisms in a population. In other words, natural selection selects alleles that have characteristics that help reproduction and survival. Alleles that increase the probability of survival and reproduction are passed on to the next generation. However, I want to argue that the heritable traits that increase the likelihood of survival, adaptation, and reproduction are created by natural selection based on certain fundamental principles. In other words, for living organisms to succeed in survival and adaptation, natural selection selects the hereditary characteristics of alleles based on certain fundamental principles. Fundamental principles: 1-energy and nutrient supply; 2-security supply; 3-adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc.; 4-reproduction. These are the fundamental principles of natural selection that, if fulfilled, increase the probability of adaptation, survival and reproduction. Previously, these fundamental principles were briefly stated by Mr. Darwin and other biologists. However, the importance, value, and very important role of these fundamental principles in the process of natural selection and evolution have received very little attention. If we explain survival, adaptation, and natural selection without these fundamental principles, the concepts of survival, adaptation, and natural selection will not be correct and these basic and important concepts of biology will be incompletely and wrongly understood.

Keywords: natural selection; selection principles; energy supply; security supply; survival principles; adaptation principles; alleles characteristics.

Introduction

Natural selection selects genes that increase the survival of the organism and reproductive success, or the success of transferring genes to the next generation. A gene that causes characteristics that help survival and transfer genes to the next generation, that characteristic is useful for the organism. 1 (Richard Dawkins, 1976) According to Darwin, a (successful) organism is one that survives and continues to reproduce. 2 (Ernest Mayer, 2002) Alleles that have characteristics that lead to the survival and reproduction of organisms are selected and maintained by natural selection. 3 (Campbell Biological, 2011). Natural selection is a process that, over successive generations, leads to the creation of hereditary traits that increase the probability of survival and reproduction of organisms in a population. In other words, natural selection is a process in which individuals adapted to the environment have a greater chance of survival and reproduction and can pass on their genes to the next generation. In contrast, individuals who are not compatible with the environment are removed from the species and cannot pass on their genes. During this process, genes adapted to the environment remain in the species. 4 (T. Ryan Gregory, 2009)

As you saw above, biologists believe that traits are selected by natural selection based on the success of organisms in survival and reproduction. What kind of characteristics does natural selection consider when it comes to success in survival, reproduction, and adaptation? But is the selection of hereditary characteristics limited by natural selection only at the level of survival and reproduction? Aren't there other characteristics that natural selection can select? What are the characteristics of these genes adapted to the environment? The characteristic of the useful gene is "success in survival and reproduction." Doesn't it have another definition? More importantly, what is the issue of choice? What was selected? Are alleles and phenotypic traits selected only based on survival and reproduction? But how does natural selection decide which traits to select and which to eliminate?

Based on the evidence I found, I show in this paper that there are fundamental principles by which natural selection measures and selects the heritable traits and characteristics of alleles based on certain principles for the survival and successful adaptation of all organisms. Fundamental principles: 1- Providing energy and nutrients; 2- Providing security; 3- Adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc.; 4- Reproduction or transfer of genes to the next generation.

What is selected by natural selection, I call fundamental principles. The basis of natural selection is these fundamental principles. The harmful and beneficial features of alleles are determined and defined based on these fundamental principles.

In other words, natural selection, to eliminate harmful traits, performs the criteria of diagnosis and selection based on these fundamental principles. If these fundamental principles are not fulfilled, adaptation, survival, and reproduction will be impossible. These are the fundamental principles that, if fulfilled, increase the probability of survival and reproduction.

If we explain survival, adaptation, and natural selection without these fundamental principles, the concepts of survival, adaptation, and natural selection will not be correct and these fundamental concepts of biology will be incomplete and misunderstood. To properly understand natural selection, we need to understand these fundamental principles. The truth is that natural selection is responsible for the creation of hereditary traits that lead to the fulfillment of these fundamental principles. Survival means that the organism has characteristics that are successful in providing all the fundamental principles.

I argue that natural selection most likely selects alleles for the successful adaptation of a population in all different types of organisms that have traits that can fulfill these fundamental principles. It can be

said that these are the fundamental principles of natural selection, the fundamental principles of adaptation, the fundamental principles of survival, and the fundamental principles of biology.

Except for selection at the molecular level and selection based on physical and chemical laws, My opinion is that most likely the choice will be based on these fundamental principles only. That is, in the process of the survival and adaptation of organisms, only these fundamental principles are selected by natural selection. Previously, these principles were stated by Mr. Darwin and other biologists. However, these principles have been incompletely explained in biology, evolution, and natural selection, and the importance and value of these fundamental principles have been given very little attention. In this article, I discuss how these fundamental principles play a very root, base, basic, and important role in the processes of evolution and natural selection.

Fundamental principles:

1-Selection by natural selection based on success in reproduction and transfer of genes to the next generation; Reproduction-Driven Natural Selection.

Didn't the first organisms (Replicator or RNA) or all other organisms, including bacteria, plants, animals, and insects, all need to multiply and reproduce or transfer their genes to the next generation to continue the generation? Genes copy themselves to be passed on to the next generation. All organisms are survival machines for reproduction and the copying of genes. Dawkins argued that genes are a prerequisite for evolution by natural selection. 5 (Dawkins, 1976) Acting through differential reproductive success, natural selection has produced a great diversity of existing reproductive tactics, each of which presumably corresponds to a local optimum that maximizes an individual organism's lifetime reproductive success in its particular environment. A body of theory on so-called reproductive "strategies" has yet to be adequately related to an independent theoretical framework on optimal foraging tactics. Some of the possible interactions and constraints between an animal's input of matter and energy via foraging and its output in offspring using these same materials are briefly considered. For example, the storage and utilization of lipids allow an organism to gather and sequester matter and energy during a period that is not suitable for successful reproduction but enables the organism to expend those materials at a later, more satisfactory time. 6 (ERIC R. PIANKA, 1976)

Reproduction can be considered one of the basic goals and principles of natural selection. Without the transfer of genes to the next generation or without reproduction, living organisms cannot continue the continuity of the generation, and there will be no children or generations, and the species will become extinct. Some reproduce through sexual reproduction and some through asexual reproduction; some reproduce by reproductive methods like mammals; and some reproduce by laying eggs. Body parts, characteristics, phenotypes, behaviors related to reproduction, and different methods of reproduction are subject to natural selection. Success in reproduction and the transfer of genes to the next generation in all organisms is their main purpose. reproduction is considered by natural selection for selection and screening.

2- Selection by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply; Energy and nutrient-driven Natural Selection.

Don't primitive organisms need energy and nutrients (organic materials) to reproduce and have children? My opinion is that one of the fundamental principles is the supply of energy and nutrients.

Natural selection is selected based on the principles of energy and nutrient supply. Providing energy and nutrients means providing all the substances that an organism needs to reproduce, survive, and perform its biological activities. Like water and oxygen, carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, iron, calcium, vitamins, and sunlight for plants, almost all the energy and nutrients of all organisms are provided by plants.

Ludwig Boltzmann (1886) suggested that natural selection was fundamentally a struggle among organisms for available energy. Alfred Lotka (1922) argued that organisms that capture and use more energy than their competition will have a selective advantage. In the evolutionary process, i.e., the Darwinian notion of evolution was based on a fundamental, generalized energy principle. Lotka understood that natural selection is essentially a competition between organisms for available energy (and thus the ability to exploit other resources), creating an evolutionary process driven by the principle of maximum energy flux. **7 (Charles A. S. Hall and Timothy McWhirter, 2023)** As mentioned above, Ludwi Boltzmann (1886) and Alfred Lotka (1922) discussed natural selection based on energy supply. In my opinion, whenever biologists discuss natural selection, they should state that it is based on fundamental principles. Providing energy and nutrients is one of the fundamental principles of natural selection, adaptation, and survival. Because many concepts and issues of evolution can be explained based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply. In many evolutionary cases, such as Darwin's Galápagos birds and the giraffe's neck, the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply must be used. If we do not use the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply in the case of Darwin's Galápagos bird beak, the giraffe neck and many other evolutionary cases, our understanding of the workings of the mechanism of natural selection will be wrong and incomplete. Because what happened in nature and caused the beaks of Darwin's Galápagos birds and the long necks of giraffes was a selection based on the supply of energy and nutrients.

Most organisms need nutrients to make organic macromolecules. There is a need for energy supply to make organic macromolecules. In short, they need energy and nutrients. All known organisms need carbon to produce organic molecules such as proteins, nucleic acids, and carbohydrates. The success of the formation and existence of life depends on the covalent bond between carbon and nitrogen, oxygen and hydrogen, and the production of sugar from carbon by plants. Carbon life can make different molecules that are necessary for the evolution of different organisms, including the biological needs necessary for survival. Organic macromolecules such as protein, carbohydrates, nucleic acids, and lipids require nutrients and energy to be made. **8 (Campbell Biology, 2011)**

What is selected by natural selection? Some characteristics provide nutrients and energy. In all known organisms, from the beginning of life until today, to survive and reproduce, they must have traits and characteristics (behaviors, body parts, phenotypes) to obtain energy and all the nutrients they need. , these traits are selected by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply. I mean the energy and nutrient supply; Different processes of catabolism to produce energy (energy supply) and the process of anabolism, which is any substance (nutrients) needed to build cell components (cytoskeleton, mitochondria, ribosomes, and other cell components; components of proteins and genes).

The Russian ecologist (G.F. Cause) cultivated two protist species, *Paramecium Aurelia* and *Paramecium caudatum*, under constant conditions. He provided them with a fixed amount of food every day. When Cause cultivated the two species separately, the population of each species grew rapidly and remained stable within the tolerance capacity of the culture medium. When Cause cultured both species together, *Paramecium caudatum* was destroyed in the culture medium. Cause argued that *Paramecium Aurelia* was nimble in obtaining food. He concluded that two species competing for a common resource could not coexist forever in the same place. **9 (Campbell Biology Book, 2011)**

Interpretation: This example shows competition based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply. If we consider natural selection as an eliminator, when there is competition between

organisms for energy and nutrients, natural selection selects and eliminates those that do not succeed in obtaining and providing energy and nutrients. Because *Paramecium caudatum* cannot provide its energy and nutrients, it is eliminated by natural selection. Those that remain and are not eliminated are those that can provide their energy and nutrients. Or, in a way, it can be said that those that can provide their energy and nutrients are preserved by natural selection. Natural selection maintains and supports *Paramecium Aurelia*, which is more adept and capable of providing its energy and nutrients. It is a selection based on success in providing energy and nutrients through natural selection. Adaptability should be defined as the ability to supply energy from various plant and animal sources, such as water, oxygen, etc. A slight superiority in energy supply (acquiring energy and nutrients, finding energy and nutrients, digesting, breaking down, transferring, and moving energy and nutrients) can lead to the elimination of a weaker competitor. Organisms that have characteristics in their alleles and phenotypes that make them successful in providing energy and nutrients will be successful in survival and reproduction. Not having the right phenotype and allele to provide energy and nutrients, or, in other words, failure to provide energy and nutrients, is equal to the death of the organism.

In my opinion, to state the truth of natural selection, i.e., as it happened in nature, it should be clearly stated what was selected. Therefore, in this example and similar examples, biologists should state that the selection that has been made is based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply so that it can be determined with what intention the process of natural selection has occurred. Energy and nutrients are among the main needs of organisms for life and reproduction. No organism can survive without energy and nutrients. Therefore, finding energy, breaking down and converting energy, and providing energy to different structures of organisms are the main tasks of natural selection.

3- Selection by natural selection based on fundamental principles of providing security; Immunity-Driven Natural Selection.

Didn't primitive creatures need security for survival and reproduction?

It has become increasingly clear that life-history patterns among vertebrates have been shaped by the plethora and variety of immunological risks associated with parasitic faunas in their environments. Immunological competence could very well be the most important determinant of lifetime reproductive success and fitness for many species. It is generally assumed by evolutionary ecologists that providing immunological defenses to minimize such risks to the host is costly in terms of necessitating trade-offs with other nutrient-demanding processes such as growth, reproduction, and thermoregulation. **10 (Robert L. Lochmiller, Charlotte Deerenberg, 2003)** Evolutionary theory predicts Immune traits to be under stabilizing selection owing to trade-offs between immune function and life-history traits. Empirical data, however, support mainly positive directional selection but also show variation in the form of selection among study systems, Immune traits, and fitness components. **11 (O. Seppälä, 2015).** For example, some species may evolve camouflage to blend in with their surroundings and avoid being seen by predators. Others may evolve defenses like spines or toxins to deter predators. These security strategies help organisms survive and reproduce, passing on their successful adaptations to future generations. Charles Darwin, in his theory of natural selection outlined in "On the Origin of Species," published in 1859, proposed that the survival and reproductive success of organisms are influenced by their ability to adapt to their environment and to secure resources necessary for survival, such as food, shelter, and protection from predators. **12 (Darwin, 1859).** This can be seen as an early recognition of the Importance of security in the context of biological survival.

This means that for organisms to survive and reproduce, they must be able to protect themselves from environmental hazards, diseases, and being killed by predators and competitors until they reach the age of reproduction. This is the same as providing security.

Providing security means all the actions, traits, behaviors, characteristics, and body parts that are done to protect and defend all the constituent parts of the body. Higher durability or safety than others can increase their reproduction. This feature or principle is favored or selected in the evolution of all organisms by natural selection. The need to provide security can have other names. The need for protection and safety. Some traits and characteristics of organisms are used to provide security. For example, the immune system of organisms, the skin of organisms, defensive enzymes, white blood cells, deer and cow horns, elephant tusks, bee and snake stings, fighting and defensive skills of animals, and more... provide security against the invasion of enemies, diseases, germs, and viruses, protection against conflicts with sexual rivals, and protection against environmental factors such as harmful rays of sunlight. Providing security, for this reason, is one of the fundamental principles of natural selection because it is chosen, selected, and screened by natural selection for successful adaptation, survival, and reproduction. Natural selection eliminates organisms that are unable to provide security themselves. In this way, the remaining organisms are the ones that can provide their security and transfer these characteristics to the next generation.

Note: The need to survive is different from the need to provide security for organisms. The need to provide security means that organisms need to protect their body structures and organs to survive. The need to survive, or the need for survival, is a broader concept, and for the survival of organisms, there is a need to provide energy and security and adapt to environmental conditions. This is the survival instinct. Survival instinct means the efforts of organisms to provide energy and security and adapt to environmental conditions.

4- Natural selection is selected based on adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, gravity, atmospheric pressure, light, wind, and many others.

Didn't all organisms need to adapt to environmental conditions? Natural selection means the selection and preference of species and individuals that are best adapted to live in certain environmental conditions. These natural selections and adaptations are based on various factors such as temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, gravity, osmotic adaptation, wind, and many other factors.

For example, thermophilic species are well adapted to high temperatures and humidity and live in tropical regions. Also, animals such as fish that live in high-pressure areas in water can adapt to these conditions. Birds that fly in higher air must be able to adapt to lower air pressure to fly well and search and find their food. If populations fail to adapt or migrate under climate change, then, as conditions become more unsuitable, extirpation and extinction may be unavoidable. **13 (Christmas, M.J., Breed, M.F., & Lowe, A.J., 2016)** Terrestrial organisms have learned to live in the gravitational field. Almost all of their body systems are gravity-dependent. However, the extent and mechanisms of this dependence remained unclear for a long time. **14 (O. L. Vinogradova, E. S. Tomilovskaya & I. B. Kozlovskaya, 2021)** Recently, there has been an increasing body of evidence indicating that compatible solutes are multifunctional molecules with stabilizing properties, hence protecting cell components from several abiotic stresses such as high salinity, osmotic adaptation, freezing, desiccation, high temperature, pressure, or oxygen radicals, functioning as chemical chaperones. **15 (Vargas, C., Argandoña, M., Reina-Bueno, M., et al., 2008)** All biological processes of life on Earth experience varying degrees of pressure. Aquatic organisms living in the deep sea, as well as chondrocyte cells of articular cartilage, are exposed to hydrostatic pressures that rise to several hundred times that of atmospheric pressure. In the case of marine larvae that disperse through the oceanic water column, pressure changes might be responsible for stress conditions during development, limiting colonization capabilities. **16 (Florence Pradillon & Françoise Gaill, 2006)**

Natural selection is selected based on adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, gravity, wind, and many other things. To survive, organisms needed other useful properties, such as adaptation to environmental conditions. Organisms cannot survive without adapting to environmental conditions. Different organisms, the characteristics required for adaptation in hot or cold environments, plants in rocky or clay soil, living in high or low light, adaptation of atmospheric pressure on land and in water, adaptation to hot or cold water environment, on land or in water, salt water or fresh water, the need to adapt to the pressure of deep sea water, the need for homeostasis or maintaining the internal balance of the body based on environmental conditions, and many other things that I call the need to adapt to environmental conditions. Fish in the sea and other fish in freshwater rivers, penguins in the pole, adaptation frogs in water and land, plants in deserts, some in snowy and rainy environments, and some environments are full of moisture. Organisms evolved based on the atmospheric pressure on Earth or in the sea and the Earth's gravity. (Perhaps if there was life on other planets, the creatures of the planet would evolve based on the atmospheric pressure and gravity of that planet.)

Note: In this article, I argue about 1-selection based on providing energy and nutrients and 2-selection based on providing security. In my opinion, these two principles have the greatest influence, tendency, and orientation in evolution and adaptation, through selection and screening by natural selection. Maybe other fundamental principles are involved in choosing and screening and selection, Like selection at the molecular level and other things that I don't know at the moment.

An example of selection based on the fundamental principles of security supply, the fundamental principles of energy and nutrients supply, Sexual selection, or the transfer of genes to the next generation.

New data and tests of the origin of the elongated neck of the giraffe, *Giraffa camelopardalis*, have provided fresh insight into the origin of this trait. All attempt to test one of two main hypotheses: that of natural selection via advantages from feeding on trees above competitors (Darwin, 1871) or intra-sexual (male-male) competition via advantages found in clubbing rivals more effectively in competition for females (Simmons & Scheepers, 1996). Both mechanisms should result in longer necks, and both are demonstrably advantageous to their bearers (Pratt & Anderson, 1982, 1985; Cameron & du Toit, 2007). Quoted from: 17 (Rob E. Simmons, Res Altwegg, 2010). One of the reasons for the lengthening of the giraffe's neck is sexual selection and male competition. In this article, I discuss the reason for the evolution of the giraffe's neck based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients and the fundamental principles of providing security. According to Darwin's theory, individuals within a population compete for limited resources, including energy sources such as food, 18 (Darwin, 1859).

1. The giraffe's long neck and legs evolved by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients. For example, In the same environment, there may be giraffes with different neck lengths. Perhaps there were other competing herbivores that competed fiercely with the short-necked giraffe for energy and nutrients. Because of this, some giraffes who had long necks managed to get their energy and nutrients from tree leaves. If something causes the loss of low shrubs, giraffes with shorter necks do not get enough food, energy, and nutrients. They do not survive to reproduce. But if some giraffes have long necks and can use the leaves of tall trees to provide energy and nutrients, they will survive and reproduce. After a few generations, the surviving giraffes will have longer necks because they can provide their energy and nutrients to survive. If a gene leads to long legs for an animal, long legs can be considered an evolutionary advantage in the environment if they help provide energy, nutrients, and security for that animal. With its long legs and long neck, the giraffe can reach the leaves on top of the trees and provide its energy and nutrients from the leaves. (Figure 1a) The selection of the long legs and tall neck of the giraffe by natural selection was due to its success in

providing energy and nutrients. If this long-necked giraffe succeeds in providing its energy and nutrients, it will most likely be successful in reproduction, so it will pass the long-necked trait, allele, and gene to its children.

2. The giraffe's long neck and legs evolved by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of security supply. Giraffes can also provide security (protect themselves) by kicking predators like lions with their long legs. Kicking the hunters violently will drive them away from the giraffe and help secure the giraffe. (Figure 1b) The long legs make the giraffe's body somewhat out of reach of predators. Even a long neck can strike predators with a whipping motion and drive predators away from the giraffe. This leads to the provide security of the giraffe. In this way, a giraffe with long legs will survive longer and probably be more successful in reproduction. But long legs are only a special case that leads to the fulfillment of fundamental biological needs, not a general case. Long legs may be useful for the giraffe, but the same long legs annoy the mouse and are not suitable.

To state the truth as it is and as it happened in nature, scientists and biologists must mention in the evolution lessons that the evolution of the giraffe's neck was by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply, and security supply. The truth is that natural selection, selected is based on these fundamental principles.

Figure 1a: It should be clearly stated that the reason for choosing the giraffe's long legs and neck is because of its success in providing energy and nutrients. With its long neck and legs, the giraffe has been able to obtain its energy and nutrients from the leaves of trees. Natural selection takes into account success in energy and nutrient supply.

Figure 1b: It should be clearly stated that one of the reasons for choosing the long and strong legs of the giraffe was to be successful in providing security. With strong and long legs, the giraffe can kick the lion hard and drive the lion away. Natural selection selects for traits that lead to security supply.

Most probably, the truth is that all cellular organelles evolved based on fundamental principles of natural selection.

Cell organelles have randomly evolved over the years through genetic mutations and natural selection. But natural selection has principles, and these cell organelles have been chosen for a specific purpose by the fundamental principles of natural selection. Each cell organelle has a specific task and function. The function of cellular organelles is to realize fundamental principles. All cellular organelles evolved through natural selection based on fundamental principles. That is, every cell organelle, directly or indirectly, is responsible for providing security, providing energy and nutrients, reproduction or transferring genes to the next generation, and adapting to environmental conditions.

Structures inside animal cells: (1) Nucleolus (2) Nucleus (3) Ribosome (4) Vesicle (5) Rough endoplasmic reticulum (6) Golgi apparatus (7) Cytoskeleton (8) Smooth endoplasmic reticulum (9) Mitochondria (10) Vacuole (11) Cytoplasm (12) Lysosome (13) Centriole.
31 (Cell Organelles - Types, Structure and their Functions.<https://byjus.com/biology/cell-organelles/>)

https://fa.wikipedia.org/wiki/File%3ABiological_cell.svg

1. Some cellular organelles were screened and selected by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply. The cell needs nutrients and energy supply and energy conversion (metabolism). For this purpose, evolution has caused cells to have structures and organelles to absorb, obtain, and convert nutrients and food to produce energy.

Mitochondria: Plants and animals need organelles called mitochondria to convert food into energy and carry out metabolism in their cells. Mitochondria provide most of the energy needed by the cell by producing ATP molecules. Plants obtain their energy through photosynthesis. Plants need chlorophyll to make and react with their food. The function of chlorophyll is photosynthesis, which means it combines carbon dioxide in the air with water drawn up by plant roots in the presence of light to produce sugars (carbohydrates) and oxygen. Mitochondria use aerobic respiration to produce ATP energy molecules. **19 (Campbell Biology 2011)**

Lysosome: The lysosome is emerging as a signaling hub that can integrate and relay external and internal nutritional information to promote cellular and organismal homeostasis, as well as a major contributor to the processing of energy-dense molecules like glycogen and triglycerides. The lysosome functions in the process of sending signals to other organs and tissues to ensure energy and nutrients. The lysosome controls cells' energy and nutrients. **20 (Vinod K. Mony, Shawna Benjamin & Eyleen J. O'Rourke 2016)** Lysosome is a bag that contains many enzymes to break down food and provide energy.

Vesicle: Vesicles can help transport materials that an organism needs to survive and recycle waste materials (provide energy and nutrients to the cell). They can also absorb and destroy toxic substances and pathogens to prevent cell damage and infection (security supply the cell). Vesicles also help store and transport materials such as proteins, enzymes, hormones, and neurotransmitters. They are a small but essential part of biological systems and processes such as: digestion and metabolism, the nervous system, kidney and liver function (to provide energy and nutrients). [21 \(Jenna Lester, Joanne Lewsley 2020\)](#) Vesicle is a bag that plays a role in transporting nutrients and providing energy.

Endoplasmic reticulum: The endoplasmic reticulum is a membrane-bound organelle in cells of eukaryotic cells involved in protein synthesis, lipid synthesis, and calcium storage. There are two types of endoplasmic reticulum: the rough type and the smooth type. The rough endoplasmic reticulum consists of flattened sacs and is where you will typically find ribosomes attached to its surface, thus giving it a rough appearance under the microscope. The smooth endoplasmic reticulum, in turn, consists of tubules and vesicles and has a rather smooth appearance because ribosomes do not typically attach to its surface. [22 \(Site source: Biology Online\)](#) The endoplasmic reticulum (ER) has many different functions. These include the translocation of proteins (such as secretory proteins) across the ER membrane; the integration of proteins into the membrane; the folding and modification of proteins in the ER lumen; the synthesis of phospholipids and steroids on the cytosolic side of the ER membrane; and the storage of calcium ions in the ER lumen and their regulated release into the cytosol, reviewed in Matlack et al., 1998; Meldolesi and Pozzan, 1998; Ma and Hendershot, 2001; McMaster, 2001. Quoted from [23 \(Gia K Voeltz, Melissa M. Rolls, Tom A Rapoport, 2002\)](#) The endoplasmic reticulum has various functions. But the most important ones related to the fundamental principles are the making and shaping of proteins. The most important function of protein is to build cell components, tissues, and body parts of organisms. The components of the cell, such as the cell wall, help to supply energy and nutrients to the cell by providing the diffusion of nutrients into the cell. Proteins make up many of the main components of the cell, whose job it is to supply the cell with energy and nutrients. Different proteins make body parts such as the liver, spleen, stomach, and intestines. The stomach, intestines, and liver are responsible for supplying energy to the body. The spleen is a part of the immune system that is responsible for the security of the body. Making proteins in the endoplasmic reticulum requires energy and nutrients. In the energy cycle, the cell can convert proteins, carbohydrates, and lipids back into energy and nutrients. [24 \(Campbell Biology, 2011\)](#) Certainly, natural selection has selected the endoplasmic reticulum based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients and providing security. Perhaps other selections at the molecular level are carried out by natural selection. But my discussion in this article about the selection is based on the fundamental principles.

Vacuole: A vacuole is a membrane-bound structure in the cytoplasm of a cell that's primarily involved in various biological processes, such as intracellular secretion, excretion, storage, and digestion. It is surrounded by a single membrane and contains various substances. Vacuoles for osmoregulation, for instance, contain water, ions, and other molecules. In plant cells wherein vacuoles are relatively large, the vacuole maintains internal hydrostatic pressure inside the cell and thereby helps plants by providing support to plant structures such as leaves and flowers. As a protective container, it can hold and isolate waste products and other harmful materials from other cellular components. The vacuole also serves as storage. For example, the vacuoles of seeds store proteins essential for seed germination. [25 \(site source: biology\)](#) Vacuoles play roles in providing nutrient recycling and allocation. They are a place to store water, food to provide energy and nutrients, excrement to provide security to cells, and also regulate the amount of water to provide energy and nutrients to the cells. Pigments in the cell vacuole protect it from harmful light, providing security to the cell. Vacuoles play

an important role in cell metabolism. The function of vacuoles is to provide energy and nutrients and provide security, according to the fundamental principles.

Golgi apparatus: This organelle lies at the heart of the secretory pathway and performs numerous functions including modification of secretory cargoes and their sorting and delivery to various destinations, which may be inside or outside the cell. The Golgi apparatus has a characteristic structure that is conserved amongst nearly all eukaryotes, comprising flattened membrane discs called cisternae that are layered on top of each other to generate the Golgi stack. Most 'lower' eukaryotes contain one or more discrete Golgi stacks per cell, while in vertebrates the stacks are typically linked to form the Golgi ribbon, a single copy structure usually found next to the centrosome. 26 (Martin Lowe, 2011) Golgi apparatus, small bags whose job it is to package and distribute provide nutrients and energy in the cell and also outside the cell. Golgi apparatus secretes an enzyme that helps the cell metabolize more easily. The Golgi apparatus has evolved by natural selection to provide energy and nutrients to the cell.

Chloroplasts: exist only in plant cells and their task is to make and store energy or food such as starch, fat, and protein. Chloroplasts are responsible for photosynthesis, or energy production, in plants. Sunlight, which is converted into chemical energy by plants, is the source of energy for all organisms. 27 (Campbell Biology, 2011) interpretation: Different plants evolved by natural selection based on the supply of energy and nutrients in different parts of the world. Some aquatic plants can absorb their energy and materials from salt water, and some from fresh water. Some plants evolved in humid areas; Some evolved in mountainous areas; and some evolved in desert areas. Their evolution and adaptation by natural selection were based on the ways and methods of providing energy and nutrients. With these interpretations, we reach this conclusion: The fact that cells evolved to have organelles to provide energy and nutrients indicates that mutations have occurred that help provide energy and nutrients to the cell. These mutations were selected by natural selection based on the principles of energy and nutrient supply and accumulated and preserved throughout history. Of course, in some organisms, the way to provide energy and nutrients is different, and this is because natural selection has created different adaptations based on the type of resources for providing energy, the amount of access to energy and nutrients, and other reasons. For example, some plants use sunlight and carbon dioxide to provide energy. Some, like herbivores, exploit plants for their energy and nutrients. Some, like carnivores, eat herbivores for energy and nutrients.

2. Selection of cellular organelles by natural selection based on fundamental principles of security supply.

Plasma membrane: ensures the safety of the cell by enclosing the contents of the cell and protecting its constituent organs from external harmful factors. This same cell membrane plays a vital role in regulating the movement of nutrients into the cell to provide energy and remove toxic substances and waste that the cell does not need and may endanger the cell's safety. The plasma membrane consists of two layers of phospholipids. 28 (Campbell Biology, 2011) According to the scientists' theory, the early RNA was accidentally trapped inside a bubble (Protocell). 29 (Dawkins, 1976). This cell wall was adopted by natural selection. Because it leads to more security and, thus, more cell survival. Inside the cell, there are enzymes to destroy invaders, remove substances harmful to the cell, and provide security to the cell. In addition to the above, the cytoplasm also contains pigments such as melanin, which leads to the formation of color in the pigmented cells of the skin. These pigments protect the cells and the internal structure of the body against the harmful effects of the sun's ultraviolet rays.

Lysosome: Lysosomes are ubiquitous membrane-bound intracellular organelles with an acidic interior. They are central for the degradation and recycling of macromolecules delivered by endocytosis, phagocytosis, and autophagy. 30 (Hann Appelqvist, Petra Wäster, Katarina Kågedal, Karin Öllinger 2013) One of the organelles of the cell is responsible for the security of the cell. The lysosome is responsible for secreting enzymes to destroy pathogenic and incapacitating agents. The organs that protect the cell against invaders were created during evolution. These cellular organs were selected and maintained by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of security. Any feature that leads to the security of cells is maintained and supported by natural selection. With this evidence, we conclude that security is one of the basic needs of cells. Because the cell can't survive and multiply without ensuring its security. If the cell does not have defense, security, and protection structures, it will be destroyed by attackers. Even security has changed in organisms during evolution, and natural selection preserves and supports Compatible and fitness options in the best possible way to ensure the security of organisms.

3. Selection of cell organelles by natural selection based on their reproduction and transfer of genes to the next generation. The cell needs to multiply, reproduce (reproduction), and grow.

Nucleus: Contains DNA (hereditary material) as well as various proteins and the nucleolus. The major functions of the cell nucleus, including transcription, pre-mRNA splicing and ribosome assembly, have been studied extensively by biochemical, genetic and molecular methods. 31 (Miroslav DUNDR; Tom MISTELI, 2001) Some cellular organelles such as the nucleus, RNA, ribosomes, and other cellular organelles were selected by natural selection for cell reproduction and sexual reproduction.

Ribosomes: are small organelles that contain RNA and specific proteins in the cytoplasm. Inside the cell, ribosomes are directly involved in building proteins using their RNA and amino acids. This process involves decoding the information contained in mRNA and using amino acids to produce the required proteins. 32 (Campbell Biology, 2011) All cells require the DAN translation process for their reproduction. Cell division, or cell proliferation, plays a vital role in survival and meeting (or providing) the needs of cells and large organisms. In this way, there are cells with various functions in the organism that multiply regularly and replace old cells to meet the fundamental and diverse needs of organisms (energy, security, etc.). Some enzymes in the cell help with the reproduction and multiplication of the cell. Cells need to reproduce to survive. What led me to the fact that cell reproduction is one of the fundamental needs of a cell, fundamental was that a cell can't survive without replicating itself. Cell division is different in eukaryotic cells. Cells divide in two ways: meiosis and mitosis. Cell division has different stages. What is important is that, without cell division, the continued survival of organisms will be compromised. In the act of reproduction, genes carefully copy and replicate cell organelles. For cell proliferation, there is a need for cell organelles and necessary materials.

4. The cell needs to move. But why did movement in cells evolve and be selected for by natural selection?

Some cells, such as sperm cells, have organelles called flagella for cell motility. Many single-celled and microscopic organisms are also motile, using methods such as flagellar motility, amoeboid movement, gliding motility, and swarming motility. It is now widely accepted that the basic engine for gliding or crawling locomotion is the actin cytoskeleton. 33 (TJ Mitchison, LP Cramer, 1996) Cell motility or migration is an essential cellular process for a variety of biological events. During embryonic development, cells migrate to appropriate locations for the morphogenesis of tissues and organs. Cells need to migrate to heal the wound in repair damaged tissue. Vascular endothelial cells (Ecs) migrate to form new capillaries during angiogenesis. White blood cells migrate to the sites of inflammation to kill bacteria. Cell migration is a multistep process that involves the integration and coordination of complex biochemical and biomechanical signals. 34 (Song Li, Jun-Lin Guan, Shu Chain 2005) Directed, purposeful movement is one of the qualities that we most closely associate with living organisms, and essentially all known forms of life on this planet exhibit some type of self-generated movement or motility. Even organisms that remain sessile most of the time, like flowering plants and trees, are quite busy at the cellular level, with large organelles, including chloroplasts, constantly racing around within cellular boundaries. Directed biological movement requires that the cell be able to convert its abundant stores of chemical energy into mechanical energy. 35 (Daniel A. Fletcher, Julie A. Theriot 2004)

Motility was selected and chosen by natural selection based on fundamental principles because it helps cells provide energy and secure themselves. A cell that moves can better obtain energy and nutrients and provide security. There is competition for energy supply, security, reproduction, and finally adaptation to environmental conditions among individuals of the same species and between species. Those with better mobility help them succeed in the competition for providing energy and nutrients, security, and reproduction. Eventually, they succeed in survival and gene transfer. 1. Cells such as red blood cells help to supply energy to different body tissues of organisms by carrying oxygen and moving with the help of blood flow inside the body. Selection is based on fundamental principles providing energy and nutrients. 2. Some cells, such as white blood cells, help the safety of organisms by moving towards harmful substances (based on fundamental principles providing security). Selection is based on providing security. 3. Movement helps cells, like sperm, move towards the egg and reproduce. Selection is based on fundamental principles the transfer of genes to the next generation.

Note: When biologists talk about cellular organelles, to understand the function and the reason for the evolution of these organelles, it should be mentioned which of the cellular organelles natural selection chose based on which of these fundamental principles.

Here, I argue that most human body parts are probably selected and evolved by natural selection based on fundamental principles.

The human body consists of various major organ systems, each composed of different organs and tissues that work together as a functional unit. Some of the main components and functions of each system are summarized below.

(1) **The integumentary system**, composed of the skin and associated structures, protects the body from invasion by harmful microorganisms and chemicals. 36 (Chuong et al. 2002) based on fundamental biological principles, A: skin provides security for the human body and protects the body from invasion by harmful microorganisms and chemicals. B: It also prevents water loss, the water important for providing energy to the human body.

(2) **The musculoskeletal system** (also referred to separately as the muscle system and the skeletal system), composed of the skeletal muscles and bones (with about 206 of the latter in adults), moves the body and protectively houses its internal organs. Movement—the intricate cooperation of muscle and nerve fibers—is how an organism interacts with its environment. The innervation of muscle cells, or fibers, permits an animal to carry out the normal activities of life. An organism must move to find food or, if it is sedentary, must have the means to bring food to itself. An animal must be able to move nutrients and fluids through its body, and it must be able to react to external or internal stimuli. Muscle cells fuel their actions by converting chemical energy in the form of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), which is derived from the metabolism of food, into mechanical energy. 37 (Albrecht von Haller A.V. Hill Jean-Martin Charcot Hugh Esmor Huxley Giovanni Alfonso Borelli, Encyclopedia Britannica, 2023) The human musculoskeletal system, like other organisms, provides its various basic needs. The musculoskeletal system helps people move with the help of muscles in their legs. A: Movement helps a lot to find food by walking with legs, grasping food with hands, and eating food with hands for energy supply, and accordingly, it has evolved in humans. B: It is also important to move to escape from enemies and provide security. C: Moving to find a sexual partner to reproduce and transfer genes to the next generation. D: Movement to adapt to environmental conditions: For example, moving to a hot or cold environment, human migration from a cold environment in winter to a temperate environment, or migration in summer to a cooler environment, which has evolved in humans to adapt to environmental conditions.

(3) **The respiratory system**, composed of the breathing passages, lungs, and muscles of respiration, obtains from the air the oxygen necessary for cellular metabolism; it also returns to the air the carbon dioxide that forms as a waste product of such metabolism. Humans need oxygen to provide their energy, and the respiratory system does this. 38 (Robert A. Klocke, Neil S. Cherniack, Ewald R. | Encyclopedia Britannica; 2023)

(4) The circulatory system, composed of the heart, blood, and blood vessels, circulates a transport fluid throughout the body, providing the cells with a steady supply of oxygen and nutrients and carrying away waste products such as carbon dioxide and toxic nitrogen compounds. ³⁹ (Michael Francis Oliver, Bernard Edward Matthews, M. Elizabeth Rogers |Encyclopedia Britannica; 2023) To do justice to the matter and as it is selected by natural selection, it should be said and mentioned that the evolution of the blood circulatory system was based on fundamental principles. A: The blood circulation system helps to energize or provide energy to transport, deliver, and move energy and nutrients to different cells and tissues of the human body (fundamental principles of energy supply). B: Also, the circulatory system collects harmful substances from the organs of the body and sends them to the kidneys or lungs for elimination to provide security for the human body (fundamental principles of security supply).

Image source : https://www.freepik.com/free-vector/human-internal-organs-infographic-poster_6168813.htm

(5) The human digestive system: is a system used in the human body for the process of digestion. The human digestive system consists primarily of the digestive tract, or the series of structures and organs through which food and liquids pass during their processing into forms absorbable into the bloodstream. The system also consists of the structures through which wastes pass in the process of elimination and other organs that contribute juices necessary for the digestive process. Composed of the mouth, esophagus, stomach, and intestines, breaks down food into usable substances (nutrients and energy), which are then absorbed from the blood or lymph. ⁴⁰ (Nicholas Carr Hightower, William Sircus, Harvey J. Dworken, Encyclopedia Britannica, 2023): A. The digestive system has been selected by natural selection based on the supply of energy and nutrients. For example, teeth evolved to break food so that food is digested more easily and helps provide energy and nutrients to the body. The tongue is responsible for tasting the food that humans need to provide energy and nutrients. The vitamins and proteins are delicious. Because the body needs them to supply its energy and nutrients. B: But the taste of spoiled food is unpleasant to the tongue because it reminds the body of safety (provide security). This selection has evolved to ensure the safety or to security supply of body tissues and cells. This system also eliminates the unusable or excess portion of the food as fecal matter to provide security.

(6) excretion, the process by which animals rid themselves of waste products and the nitrogenous by-products of metabolism. Through excretion, organisms control osmotic pressure—the balance between inorganic ions and water—and maintain acid-base balance. The process thus promotes homeostasis, the constancy of the organism's internal environment. Every organism, from the smallest protist to the largest mammal, must rid itself of the potentially harmful by-products of its vital activities. This process in living things is called elimination, which may be considered to encompass all of the various mechanisms and processes by which life forms dispose of or throw off waste products, toxic substances, and dead portions of the organism. The nature of the process and the specialized structures developed for waste disposal vary greatly with the size and complexity of the organism. Kidneys have

evolved in multicellular animals as a highly sophisticated channel for waste disposal, and they function to regulate the levels of water, salts, and organic materials in the bodies of higher animals. Materials eliminated via the kidney include nitrogenous waste products (ammonia, uric acid, urea, creatine, creatinine, and amino acids), excess quantities of salts and water that may be taken into the body, and various other organic materials produced by life-sustaining chemical reactions. Functionally, the kidney is a microfilter that initially removes dissolved as well as some suspended materials from the circulatory system, along with large quantities of water. These substances are differentially reabsorbed into the blood by various kidney structures during urine formation, to a degree that varies considerably throughout the animal kingdom. For example, animals that absorb large quantities of water into their bodies (such as freshwater fish) excrete copious quantities of water in their urine. The reverse is true of many desert animals, which must conserve water and therefore produce thick, semisolid urine. The kidney, in its various stages of evolution, functions at the expense of considerable metabolic energy and cannot be considered to be a passive system. 41 (Fenton Crosland Kelley, James Arthur Ramsay, 2023 Britannica) The excretory system, composed of the kidneys, ureters, urinary bladder, and urethra, removes toxic nitrogen compounds and other wastes from the blood to provide security to the human body.

(7)The nervous system, is an organized group of cells specialized for the conduction of electrochemical stimuli from sensory receptors through a network to the site at which a response occurs. All living organisms can detect changes within themselves and in their environments. Changes in the external environment include those of light, temperature, sound, motion, and odor, while changes in the internal environment include those in the position of the head and limbs as well as in the internal organs. Once detected, these internal and external changes must be analyzed and acted upon to survive. As life on Earth evolved and the environment became more complex, the survival of organisms depended on how well they could respond to changes in their surroundings. One factor necessary for survival was a speedy reaction or response. Since communication from one cell to another by chemical means was too slow to be adequate for survival, a system evolved that allowed for faster reactions. That system was the nervous system, which is based on the almost instantaneous transmission of electrical impulses from one region of the body to another along specialized nerve cells called neurons. The simplest type of response is a direct one-to-one stimulus-response reaction. A change in the environment is the stimulus; the reaction of the organism to it is the response. Nervous systems are of two general types: diffuse and centralized. In the diffuse type of system, found in lower invertebrates, there is no brain, and neurons are distributed throughout the organism in a netlike pattern. In the centralized systems of higher invertebrates and vertebrates, a portion of the nervous system has a dominant role in coordinating information and directing responses. This centralization reaches its culmination in vertebrates, which have a well-developed brain and spinal cord. Impulses are carried to and from the brain and spinal cord by nerve fibers that make up the peripheral nervous system. 42 (Solomon D. Erulkar, Thomas L. Lentz 2023 Britannica)

Primitive animals would likely have had relatively simple nervous systems equipped primarily to detect food (1. Based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrients), avoid inhospitable environments. (2. Selection based on the basic principles of compatibility with environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc.) and locate mates (3. Selection is based on reproduction and the transfer of genes to the next generation). The appearance of the first macropredators during the Cambrian would have changed the selective landscape dramatically, likely driving the evolution of complex sense organs, sophisticated sensory processing systems, and diverse effector systems involved in capturing prey and avoiding predation (security supply, energy supply). 43 (Gregory A. Wray, 2015)

Note: As you have seen above, the nervous system in the Cambrian period was most likely evolved by natural selection based on fundamental principles.

(8) The endocrine system, composed of the hormone-secreting glands and tissues, provides a chemical communications network for coordinating various body processes for provide energy and for provide security and for reproduction and adaptation to environmental. The endocrine system assumes a primary role for maintaining energy homeostasis within the body. In coordination with the nervous system, the endocrine system is responsible for regulating hormonal responses to control the use and storage of energy molecules in order to meet the physiological demands of the body and ensure proper cellular functioning. These actions are essential for human survival as they allocate the energy necessary to operate in ever-changing environments: supplying the brain with enough glucose to think and perceive, to digest nutrients, to ready the body to external threats (ie fight-or-flight), to reproduce, etc. [44 \(Vivien Cheng, Paul Cottrell, John Mark Johnson, Amrit Sanal, 2018\)](#) As you can see above, the endocrine system has evolved based on fundamental principles. In other words, endocrine glands by natural selection, for 1. Providing energy and nutrients; for 2. Providing security; for 3. Compatibility with environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, and pressure; for 4. Reproduction and the transfer of genes to the next generation evolved.

(9) The reproductive system, composed of the male or female sex organs, enables reproduction and thereby ensures the continuation of the species and the transfer of genes. Richard Dawkins and many other biologists believe that living organisms were designed to copy genes. For this purpose, living organisms reproduce to copy genes and transfer them to the next generation. [45 \(Dawkins, 1976\)](#) The reproductive system in humans and other living organisms has evolved to reproduce and transfer genes to the next generation by natural selection. The human reproductive system is the organ system by which humans reproduce and bear live offspring. The essential features of human reproduction are (1) liberation of an ovum, or egg, at a specific time in the reproductive cycle; (2) internal fertilization of the ovum by spermatozoa, or sperm cells, (3) transport of the fertilized ovum to the uterus, or womb, (4) implantation of the blastocyst, the early embryo developed from the fertilized ovum, in the wall of the uterus, (5) formation of a placenta and maintenance of the unborn child during the entire period of gestation, (6) birth of the child and expulsion of the placenta, and (7) suckling and care of the child. For this biological process to be carried out, certain organs and structures are required in both the male and the female. The source of the ova (the female germ cells) is the female ovary; that of the spermatozoa (the male germ cells) is the testis. In females, the two ovaries are situated in the pelvic cavity; in males, the two testes are enveloped in a sac of skin, the scrotum, lying below and outside the abdomen. Besides producing the germ cells, or gametes, the ovaries and testes are the source of hormones that cause the full development of secondary sexual characteristics and also the proper functioning of the reproductive tracts. These tracts comprise the fallopian tubes, the uterus, the vagina, and associated structures in females and the penis, the sperm channels (epididymis, ductus deferens, and ejaculatory ducts), and other related structures and glands in males. The function of the fallopian tube is to convey an ovum, which is fertilized in the tube, to the uterus, where gestation (development before birth) takes place. The function of the male ducts is to convey spermatozoa from the testis, store them, and, when ejaculation occurs, eject them with secretions from the male glands through the penis. [46 \(Human Reproductive System: Definition, Diagram & Facts | Britannica\)](#)

10- The vision and hearing system During their lifetime, animals must perform many tasks, including finding food, avoiding predators, attracting mates, and navigating a complex and dynamic environment. As a result, they have evolved an astonishing array of sensory organs that are essential for survival and reproduction and shape much of their evolution and behavior. [47 \(Martin Stevens, 2013\)](#). The vision and hearing systems both evolved To provide energy and nutrients, provide security, adapt to environmental conditions, and transfer genes to the next generation in animals and humans. 1. Hearing and vision help humans identify dangers and enemies and provide security. Like hearing the voices of a lion and a leopard, the voices of human enemies can alert a person and help ensure his safety. 2. Hearing and sight help humans find game and tree fruit to provide energy and

nutrients. For example, hearing the sound of the river and water, hearing the sound of animals, and seeing the fruits and seeds of plants. 3. Also, hearing and vision help humans adapt to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc. 4. Humans can find a mate for reproduction with the help of hearing and vision. There are different types of cells in the human body; in fact, some of them directly and some indirectly function to provide energy, provide security, reproduce, and adapt to environmental conditions. In other words, if we pay close attention, the different cells of the body that make up the different tissues of the body, all by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, i.e., 1) supply of energy and nutrients (all the substances that the body needs), 2) Provide security, 3) compatibility with environmental conditions, and 4) transfer genes to the next generation, were selected.

Note: When biologists talk about the evolution of human body organs, to understand the function and reason for the evolution of human body organs, it should be mentioned which of the human body organs were selected based on which of the fundamental principles of natural selection. By examining all the organs of the human body, we conclude that each of the organs of the human body was evolved by natural selection for a specific function, i.e., to directly or indirectly realize these fundamental principles. If the Evolution of the parts of the human body is explained without using these fundamental principles, the explanation will be incomplete and wrong. If we examine all the structures and characteristics of plants and animals, vertebrates, mammals, fungi, and different single cells, they all evolved based on these fundamental principles.

The evolution of tetrapods, or the purpose of foot evolution, is based on fundamental principles.

Walking tetrapods and finding food: several extant fishes have several morphological and behavioral traits that facilitate moving out of the water to escape predation, find food or new habitats, or lay eggs. The most simplistic and least anatomically derived method to move across a dry horizontal surface is to undulate or flip the body by modifying the same motor programs that facilitate swimming and escape responses in water, as is seen in eels, killifishes, and sticklebacks. 48 (Brooke E. Flammang, Apinun Suvarnaraksha, ...Daphne Soares 2016)

The above text that I brought from an article clearly shows the evolution of fish to tetrapods and their exit from the water to escape from predators, find food, and create a new habitat for reproduction, that is, the evolution of tetrapods or the evolution of legs, which was based on fundamental principles. Natural selection has chosen the traits that lead to the realization of fundamental principles. 1. Escape from being hunted means that the evolution of the foot is useful for ensuring one's safety. 2. The purpose of the evolution of the foot is to find food to provide energy and nutrients. 3- Finding a habitat for laying

eggs using legs means the evolution of walking or the evolution of legs to aid reproduction and transfer genes to the next generation.

The evolution of different wings and legs in vertebrates based on the fundamental principles.

Vertebrate limb diversity was produced by changes in the number, position and shape of structures that can be traced to Ordovician (463–439 Myr) through Late Devonian (409–362 Myr) fossils. The demands of feeding and locomotion in the Ordovician and Silurian seas led to a surprising variability of the earliest known appendages: some forms possessed a continuous anterior fin that ran the length of the body, others had paired fins that projected immediately behind a head shield, and still other primitive vertebrates had no paired fins at all. Some regions of vertebrate appendages are more variable than others; the invention of flippers, wings, and other specialized limbs often involved significant changes in the pattern of distal structures rather than proximal ones. 49 (Shubin, N., Tabin, C., & Carroll, S. Fossils, 1997)

The evolution of legs in amphibians, reptiles, and mammals and the evolution of wings in birds and bats have been based on fundamental principles. Legs and wings are for the movement of vertebrates for energy and nutrient supply and security supply, adapting to environmental conditions, and transferring genes to the next generation. 1. For example, birds can fly away from ground predators, which is useful for security supply. 2. Also, by flying with their wings, birds can go to different places to find water and food and supply their energy and nutrients. 3. Wings also help birds migrate to a warm and temperate place in the cold season and adapt themselves to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity. 4. By flying, birds can find a mate to transfer genes to the next generation.

Important note: Ecology and morphology of living things should be studied based on fundamental principles.

The first evidence to confirm natural selection was selective coloration.

During his research from 1849 to 1860, Henry Walter Bates saw butterflies that were not naturally poisonous in the virgin forests of Brazil. But in terms of patterns, they imitated poisonous species. As soon as a pattern of new colors and patterns was found in the poisonous butterfly, the non-poisonous butterfly imitated it. In 1864, Fritz Muller discovered that poisonous species mimic each other's colors. Thus, the insectivorous birds eating one type of these poisonous butterflies was enough to avoid eating others that were similar and the same color as this type. In this way, several types imitated each other, and much fewer were killed by enemies. 50 (Ernest Mayer, 2002)

Interpretation; Poisonous butterfly moths use poison to repel attackers from themselves so they don't get killed. Or their cheek poison keeps them safe from predators. Thus, if an insectivorous bird eats a

poisonous butterfly and becomes ill, it will never eat that butterfly again. A non-toxic butterfly can provide security by imitating the color of poisonous butterflies. Natural selection favors butterflies that can take care of themselves or provide themselves security. This selection is based on the fundamental principles of providing security. The non-poisonous butterfly protects itself by imitating the shape and color of the poisonous butterfly (security supply).

An example of selection based on energy and nutrient supply.

Darwin's Galápagos bird beak interpretation. In the Galapagos Islands, Darwin observed four types of finches with different beaks. But why are there four types of finches with different beaks in the Galapagos Islands?

Galápagos finches are one of the most famous examples of evolution, and their name will forever be associated with Charles Darwin's journey and his theory of natural selection. Due to the variety of beak sizes and shapes, each species is adapted to a specific type of food. *Geospiza* has a thick beak that is adapted for eating hard seeds. *Camarhynchus pallidus* even uses cactus spines and thin tree branches to pull arthropods out of tree holes. **51 (What is evolution?, Ernst Meyer)** Suppose there are two types of finches (Darwin's finches) on an island, each of which obtains the energy and nutrients it needs from different sources. For example, one type of bird uses insects, and another uses plant seeds to provide energy and nutrients.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File%3ADarwin%27s_finches.jpeg

Evolution and natural selection work on bird beaks in different environments, changing the shape of birds' beaks based on their energy and nutrient needs. (I just remind you that changing the shape of the beak to provide energy and nutrition is only one example of the traits for provide energy to the organisms. To energy supply; in addition to changing the beak, there must be changes in the intestines, stomach, metabolism, thermal balance of the body, etc.) If an island has plant food sources that produce large seeds and other food sources, such as insects, are limited, finches with large and strong beaks will survive and reproduce. But why? Finches that have this large beak are better able to break the seeds and eat their contents, and they are less likely to starve. Therefore, this type of bird can provide the energy and nutrients it needs by breaking hard seeds with its large beak. But finches that feed on insects cannot supply their energy and nutrients due to the lack of insects. Therefore, for those who can only feed on insects, their population will decrease or disappear completely.

On the other hand, the second island has abundant food sources of insects, and scarce sources of plant seeds to provide finches with energy and nutrients. On the second island, Any creature that can provide its energy and nutrients survives. Evidence obtained from Darwin's research showed that finch birds, with narrow and sharp beaks, survive and reproduce more on this island, where there are many insects. **52 (What is evolution?, Ernst Meyer)** The reason is that there are many insects on this island. They have narrow and sharp beaks, can hunt insects better, and are less hungry. According to the fundamental principles, birds survive because they can get the energy and nutrients they need from insects. Over time, these different patterns of energy supply based on beak shape (as a heritable trait) can change the beak shape of any population. For example, the population of the first island may have been selected

by the principle of energy supply and moved towards larger and stronger beaks to obtain their energy from plant seeds. Because on this island, only this type can provide its energy and nutrients. Selection based on providing energy and nutrients would have made the population of the second island have thinner and sharper beaks to provide their energy from insects, and only this type would survive. Finally, it appears that the two populations or two types of finches are somewhat different. This hypothesis answers the question much better than previous theories: why are the beaks of Darwin's Galápagos birds different? Each beak is adapted to a specific type of food to provide energy and nutrients. Here the same Darwinian laws apply: beneficial changes that lead to provide energy and nutrients are maintained by natural selection, thus fundamental principles driving evolution.

Regarding the types of beaks of Darwin's Galápagos birds, it should be mentioned that the reason for the evolution of these beaks was by natural selection based on the supply of energy and nutrients, so that the truth is clear to us and others. If the evolution of the types of Galápagos birds' beaks, the reason for the evolution is not explained according to these fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply, the explanation and interpretation will be incomplete.

Interpretation of the reason for the abundance of black moths in the industrial era of England based on fundamental principles

The rapid spread of a novel black form (known as carbonara) of the peppered moth *Biston betularia* in 19th-century Britain is a textbook example of how an altered environment may produce morphological adaptation through genetic change. ⁵³ (Arjen E van't Hof, Nicola Edmonds, Martina Dalíková, František Marec, Ilik J Saccheri, 2011)

From the beginning, several reasons have been proposed for changes in melanic gene frequency in the pepper moth *Biston betularia* and other industrial melanic moths. These include the higher innate fitness of melanic forms and selective predation for camouflage. The existence and possible origin of the heterozygous advantage are discussed. Since the 1950s, as a result of empirical evidence, selective predation has become the preferred explanation and is undoubtedly the main cause of frequency change. ⁵⁴ (LM Cook, Ilik J. Saccheri, 2013)

Interpretation of the cause of the abundance of black butterflies based on the fundamental principles: The trees were darkened due to the smoke caused by the Industrial Revolution. The black butterfly is well camouflaged among the black soot and is rarely hunted by birds. But The white butterfly is easier to see among the black soot and is hunted by birds. The black butterfly amid black soot provides better security than the white butterfly. This shows the importance of providing security. The survival of the black butterfly has been selected based on providing security. The black butterfly has been more successful in securing itself. A white butterfly cannot camouflage in a dark place. Therefore, his security is not provided, and he is easily removed by natural selection. But, because the security of the black butterfly is provided, they reproduce and their population increases.

The following example shows how providing security as a fundamental principle is selected by natural selection and causes evolution, adaptation, and survival.

The skin color of many animals is similar to that of the environment. This makes them hidden from the eyes of others, especially rivals and enemies. Since living organisms have different colors to hide in the

environment, color change has been developed based on adaptation to the environment. Animals that protected themselves better than others lived longer and reproduced more than their competitors. In this example, two groups of mice live in a new area with black rocks due to a genetic mutation with inherited variation in coat or skin color, one black mouse and the other yellowish brown mice. In this environment with black earthy stones, birds of prey recognize brown mice better than black mice among black stones. Since brown mice are easily seen by birds of prey, large numbers of brown mice are hunted, and far fewer black mice are hunted. In this way, the proportion of black mice in the population increases.

The image on the left shows that a population of rats has entered or spawned in an area where the surrounding rocks are very dark. As a result of natural genetic variation, some of these mice are black and some are brown. The picture on the left shows that the population of brown and black mice is equal. The middle image shows that brown mice are more visible to birds of prey and less secure. Therefore, brown mice are eaten more often than black mice. The image on the right shows only the remaining black mice that managed to secure themselves (security supply) better than the brown mice. Mice whose immunity is provided for any reason reach reproductive age and produce children. Therefore, based on the fundamental principles of selection based on providing security, the abundance of black mice will increase in the next generation.

Coat color is an inherited trait in all organisms. This is a trait that can be passed from parent to child, so an increase in the proportion of black mice in the remaining population means an increase in the proportion of black mice in the next generation. After several generations of selection based on safety, the population may consist entirely of black mice. This population change has occurred by natural selection because black mice provide better security. Mouse color, which leads to better or less security, is a heritable trait that causes variation in populations. An important point to pay attention to is that sometimes useful traits, organs, and behaviors provide energy and security in an environment with special conditions and are desirable in this environment. However, the same traits may not be useful in another environment and may even be harmful to some organisms. In the sense that they cannot provide his energy and security.

In the example of black and yellow mice mentioned above, the reason why black mice become more abundant than brown mice in successive generations is not because they are more evolved. Rather, it is because they have an inherited trait that allows them to secure themselves (provide security) in that environment. This makes the rats last longer and reproduce in that particular environment (black earth). In a different environment, for example, where the color of the stones is bright and white or yellow, it is possible to change the position of favorable and unfavorable attributes. That is, in this environment, black mice are hunted more, and white and yellow mice are hunted less. This causes the proportion of yellow and white mice to increase in the population. They were able to provide security in this special environment. Therefore, more yellow and white mice reproduce because it provides security. Many offspring of rats use these useful traits that protect them in that particular environment. Therefore, their children will increase and pass on useful features to the next generation. We should note that in this environment with the stones bright and white or yellow, white and yellow mice can not only be more secure but also have more energy, reproduction, and movement. Providing security in this environment will help them to move more; probably, by moving more, they can find food for themselves and supply

their energy and nutrients. Movement helps them find mates, reproduce, and transfer genes. In other words, providing security makes other fundamental principles better realized.

Interpreting the relationship between plants, herbivores, and carnivores in ecology using fundamental principles.

In ecology, it should be clearly stated that ecological changes sometimes occur in connection with the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply. For example, a change in the level of soil nutrients and a change in light energy can be effective in the multiplication and reproduction of plants. A change in the plant population will bring about a change in the herbivore population. Because herbivores get their energy and nutrients from plants. Also, the change in the population of herbivores, which occurred due to the change in the population of plants, brings about a change in the population of carnivores. Because carnivores get their energy and nutrients from herbivores. In other words, the energy of carnivores depends on herbivores. Also, the energy of herbivores depends on plants. The energy of plants depends on water, light, nutrients in the soil, and carbon dioxide. The relationship between these should be analyzed based on the ability to supply energy from another level. If there are plenty of nutrients, light, water, and any other substances that plants need to provide their energy, the number of reproduction and survival of plants will also increase. If the number of plants increases, the number of herbivores whose energy is provided by plants will also increase through reproduction. In this way, many carnivores can provide their energy and nutrients for reproduction and survival from many herbivores.

Species and populations survive and are better able to provide security than competitors. By better here, I mean more adaptable.

For example, consider two populations of buffalos, one of which has large and sharp horns for defense. But another population does not have such horns. Hence, horns evolved to function as weapons inflicting damage; as defense organs shielding their owner; as binding organs allowing opponents a secure lock in battle; and as display organs having an a priori intimidating effect on certain conspecifics. **55 (Geist, Valerius, 1966)** When faced with enemies and hunters, the population, which has large and sharp horns, wounds the attackers to death. Defense with big and sharp weapons provides their security. But those without big and sharp horns are more likely to be hunted, and their population will decrease. If a small group of buffalos with large and sharp horns migrates to a population that does not have large and sharp horns, they will mix through gene mixing (reproduction). Genes with large and sharp horns spread in the population. Because this feature has provided their security, it keeps the ones with horns alive, spreads in the population, and changes the population. The distribution of the frequency of the sharp horn allele among the population was most likely due to selection based on providing security. Because it provides security for its owner. Perhaps, in some cases, sexual selection is effective in decreasing and increasing the frequency of the sharp horn allele.

An example of the selection of alleles by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of providing security

Drosophila melanogaster has an allele that makes it resistant to several types of insecticides, including DDT. The frequency of this allele in the laboratory strain of *Drosophila melanogaster* in the early 1930s (before the use of DDT) was zero percent. However, in the strains that originated from the wild types collected in 1960 (with more than 30), the frequency of this allele reached 37%. One hypothesis says that the aforementioned alleles arose as a result of mutations between 1930 and 1960. Another hypothesis says, It is possible that this allele was present in the population in 1930, but it was very rare. In both cases, the increase in the frequency of the DDT resistance allele has occurred because the insecticide DDT, as a very strong poison, has created a strong natural selection force in the *Drosophila*

population. Individuals from the population that did not develop resistance to DDT would die out. Few people who have the allele resistant to the poison reproduce and pass on the property of resistance to the poison to the next generation. The frequency of the allele that causes resistance to the poison will increase in the population that has been exposed to the poison. 56 (Campbell Biology, 2011) These changes are not random. Rather, natural selection, by preferring the alleles that maintain and provide the safety (security) of the individuals in the population, causes survival and adaptive evolution. Natural selection will eliminate individuals from the population who cannot protect (provide security) themselves against DDT. But for those who have the allele to provide security against the insecticide, evolution leads to their adaptation to their living environment. In this example, the selection via natural selection was based on the principles of providing security, And adaptive evolution has occurred for the intention and cause and purpose of securing the safety (providing security) of *Drosophila*. Natural selection preserves any allele that helps secure (provide security) organisms.

An example of selection by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of providing security

I would like to argue here that providing security is one of the fundamental principles of natural selection that is selected. In Indonesia, a carrier crab carries a sea urchin on its back. This is for his protection. When the attacking fish attacks it, the crab pulls the sea urchin towards the fish, thus the fish gives up hunting the crab. Sometimes crabs use jellyfish to secure themselves. 57 (Campbell Biology, 2011) Why has this behavior evolved in this type of crab? When an attacking fish attacks a crab, the crab pulls the sea urchin towards the fish, thus providing its security. This work has evolved to provide security. Natural selection chooses the behavior that leads to success in securing the security of organisms and maintains and accepts it. In some organisms, behaviors have evolved to ensure their safety (provide security) by carrying other organisms. Success in securing the security of organisms is an important factor in the success survival and reproduction of organisms. The important point is that security is an important evolutionary trait that is subject to natural selection.

Populations adapt and evolve through natural selection based on the fundamental principles of providing energy. An example of adaptation and density of the population (the reason for the increase and decrease of the deer population)

Reindeer migrated to Isla Royale, in Lake Superior between Canada and the United States, by swimming or by the lake freezing. After that, the wolves migrated to that island due to the freezing of the lake. The lake has not frozen in recent years. So the population of wolves and reindeer did not migrate in and out. However, studies show that in this century, the deer population has fluctuated and has drastically decreased or greatly increased. The reason for this decrease in population is the unfavorable weather and the cold weather the weakening of the deer, the decrease in food, and low access to food sources. With favorable weather and an abundance of food, the deer population has increased. When wolves feed on deer, the wolf population has increased and the deer population has decreased. But a balance must be established. Because the population of wolves has increased and the population of deer has decreased. So there is not enough food for wolves. 58 (Campbell Biology, 2011) **Commentary:** In this way, with the decline of the reindeer population, many wolves cannot get their energy and nutrients from deer, so they die and the wolf population decreases. If there is plenty of greens and grass to provide energy and nutrients for the deer, the deer population will increase again. But a balanced cycle is established. Factors such as hunting by wolves and the growth of parasites reduce the deer population again. Deer populations may weaken and disappear due to the occurrence of weather that they are not compatible with, such as cold weather. In cold weather, the feed to supply

their energy and nutrients is reduced, and deer cannot supply their energy and nutrients. Without providing energy and nutrients, survival and reproduction become very difficult and even impossible. Providing energy and nutrients is considered the basic biological rule for success in survival and reproduction. Without energy and nutrients, survival and reproduction are impossible. Natural selection works and selects based on the supply of energy and nutrients or the failure to supply energy and nutrients. This example shows that what causes the increase and decrease of populations depends on the success in the realization of these fundamental principles. The increase and decrease of the wolf and deer population occurs based on the success of the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients. The growth of parasites depends on the supply of energy and nutrients from deer. 1. If the deer can protect itself against parasites and wolves (security supply), 2. The deer adapts to environmental conditions such as cold temperatures, 3. There should be enough plants to provide energy and nutrients for the deer, 4. It is likely that there will be more deer reproduction and the deer population will increase.

Another example of selection by natural selection is based on the fundamental principles of security supply and energy supply.

I show here that successful adaptations are selected by natural selection based on success in providing energy and security. Mr. Darwin says; On the mother island, there are strong winds that blow winged insects into the sea. Insects of the same type found in other parts of the world with wings are the same type of insects on this island without wings. Environmental conditions have made the ratio of wingless insects to winged insects higher. Wingless insects exist on the islands as a result of natural selection and disuse. Call it a combination of disuse and natural selection. 59 (Darwin, 1859)

New interpretation; But the more correct theory is that their lack of wings was chosen based on the principles of providing security. The wing threatens the security of the insect. Those that had wings on this island were blown into the sea by the wind. Now, some of these types of insects are wingless, and for those who don't have wings, their safety is ensured. Because those without wings were not blown into the sea by the wind. So they didn't need wings. Or rather, on this island, all those insects that were thrown into the sea by the wind disappeared. But changes appeared in a wingless insect. This insect is not thrown into the sea by the wind, and its number has increased on this island. The wings threatened the security of these insects. It means that those who had wings were not safe. Insects without wings were more secure. In these organisms, security has been selected, and wingless insects evolved on this island.

The evolution of flight In organisms has been selected by natural selection to provide energy. Darwin mentions that on some of these islands, these same insects feed on flowers (they get their energy from flowers). Not only have wings not disappeared, but they have evolved. 60 (Darwin, 1859) According to the fundamental principles, because these insects get their energy from flowers, they need to move with wings and fly to reach the flowers. Therefore, through the basic mechanism of natural selection, evolution has favored winged locomotion to provide energy to these insects. Success in energy provision is selected by natural selection.

Selection at the beginning of life by natural selection is based on the supply of energy and nutrients; evolution at the beginning of life is based on the supply of energy and nutrients.

The chemical compatibility of sulfur and its abundance in prebiotic Earth as reduced sulfide (H₂S) have made it a source of life 3.8 billion years ago and also the main source of early evolutionary energy. A dramatic increase in ambient oxygen about 600 million years ago led to the end of H₂S as an energy source, and H₂S-dependent animals either became extinct, displaced, or adapted to sulfide energy. The

simplest definition of life is the ability to use and control energy. Today, almost all the energy of life comes from the sun. Plants oxidize water to oxygen and reduce inorganic carbon, while animals obtain energy by reversing this process. 61 (Kenneth R. Olson, Karl D. Straub, 2015)

interpretation; I interpret the above in a new way that better explains the evolution of the first organisms. H₂S has been the most primitive source of energy for life. 600 million years ago, evolution took place, and the adaptation for providing energy changed to oxygen. Remember that natural selection only selected this new adaptation 600 million years ago to improve energy supply. Oxygen in H₂S can produce more ATP for energy. Selection was based on energy supply, and these changes and mutations were accepted.

The emergence of life on early Earth required the presence of at least three different substances and related physical properties: liquid water, a source of free energy (need for energy), and organic compounds capable of self-assembly (need for reproduction). Liquid water is essential for all primitive and modern life, and the existence of life in the absence of water is very impossible. Potential energy sources for life include sunlight and energy from chemical imbalances in underwater or underground sites. Self-assembling compounds must be available to form building blocks for polymer synthesis and the formation of boundary structures. Perhaps the most important definition of life is that the entire molecular system must be able to reproduce itself using genetically encoded self-assembly of components and polymerization reactions. In a population of reproductive systems competing for energy and nutrients (competition for energy supply), changes cause changes in individual molecular systems that affect growth and reproductive efficiency. A population of finite molecular systems can then be subjected to the kinds of selection processes required for Darwinian evolution. The essential role of membrane boundaries is to create a selective permeability barrier that is necessary to separate the cytoplasm from the external environment. Cell membranes help provide security by keeping out enemies and harmful substances, and they also help provide energy and cellular metabolism by facilitating the entry of nutrients. All of these functions require membrane-associated proteins that may be present in primitive forms. Thus, it appears that the membrane boundaries of primary cells simply form a selective permeability barrier that allows essential nutrients (substances needed to provide energy and nutrients) to pass through but retains the primary biosynthetic polymer products... In a population of reproductive systems competing for energy and nutrients, changes induce changes in individual molecular systems that affect growth and reproductive efficiency. 62 (Alain Monnard, David W. Deamer, 2002)

The most important point is that selection based on the provision of energy and nutrients has existed since the beginning of life and has led to the creation of different methods of providing energy and nutrients. This shows how important natural selection is to the selection of energy and nutrient supply for adaptation, survival, and reproduction. Materials to provide the energy used for self-replication have focused on quantitative chemistry. The evolution was gradually towards the adaptation of more efficient sources of energy supply. It has been mentioned above that the competition for energy supply has been intense. Therefore, some may not have been able to provide their energy. Their removal was only due to the failure of the energy supply. It is better to explain Darwin's selection process mentioned above based on energy supply from now on.

Darwin's and Lewontin principles of natural selection

The principle of natural selection as the motive force for evolution was framed by Darwin in terms of a "struggle for existence" on the part of organisms living in a finite and risky environment. The logical skeleton of his argument, however, turns out to be a powerful predictive system for changes at all levels of biological organization. As seen by present-day evolutionists, Darwin's scheme embodies three principles: 1. Different individuals in a population have different morphologies, physiologies, and

behaviors (the principles of phenotypic variation). 2. Different phenotypes have different rates of survival and reproduction in different environments (the principles of differential fitness). 3. There is a correlation between parents and offspring in the contribution of each to future generations (the principles of reproduction, fitness is heritable). These three principles embody the principle of evolution by natural selection. 63 (Richard C Lewontin)

The principles of Lewontin and Darwin are very important in biology. In my opinion, it is more correct to explain Lewontin's principles based on fundamental principles. Diversity, in fact, means diversity in these fundamental principles. It means diversity in providing energy and nutrients, diversity in providing security, diversity in adapting to environmental conditions, and diversity in the amount and methods of reproduction. Useful variations can directly and indirectly contribute to the realization of fundamental principles. For example, if in a population some have diversity in obtaining energy, some in energy storage, and some in digestion, absorption, breakdown, and metabolism of energy, these variations can help in providing energy and nutrients and the survival of the population if the environmental conditions change. Like Galápagos birds, which only feed on insects, they will become extinct if insects become scarce. But if there is diversity in obtaining energy and nutrients and the beak of some is large enough to use fruit seeds to provide energy and nutrients, this bird with a large beak will survive and pass on the characteristic of a large beak to children. They form a new population with large beaks. Natural selection works when there is a difference in the provision of energy and nutrients, security and adaptation to environmental conditions, and the transfer of genes to the next generation or reproduction. Natural selection operates non-randomly. That is, natural selection takes things into account and most likely acts based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients, providing security, adapting to environmental conditions, reproductive success, and transferring genes to the next generation. Perhaps it is better to say that natural selection means these fundamental principles

Conclusion

As you have seen, in this article, I propose an integrated model of the fundamental principles of survival, adaptation, and natural selection. Probably all or most of the heritable traits affecting survival and adaptation by natural selection have characteristics according to fundamental principles. Fundamental principles: 1- characteristics for adaptation to provide energy and nutrients; 2- characteristics for adaptation to provide security; 3- characteristics for adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, wind, etc.; and 4- characteristics for adaptation in reproduction and transfer of genes to the next generation. What happens in the process of natural selection? Natural selection emphasizes survival and reproduction. I have shown that natural selection cares about and takes into account fundamental principles for survival and adaptation. In my opinion, selection is where it has to select certain traits for adaptation, survival, and reproduction. But it is more precise that natural selection should select certain traits for providing energy and nutrients, providing security, adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, etc., reproduction, and the transfer of genes to the next generation. If the fundamental principles are fulfilled, the possibility of adaptation, survival, and reproduction increases. In all organisms throughout the history of evolution, i.e., since the beginning of life until today, success in reproduction, adaptation, and survival of all organisms has been achieved by natural selection according to these fundamental principles. If we explain survival, adaptation, and natural selection without these fundamental principles, the concept of survival, adaptation, and natural selection will not be correct.

If we consider natural selection to be eliminative, what characteristics are those that are eliminated by natural selection lacking? What are the characteristics of those that were not eliminated and succeeded in survival and reproduction? Natural selection destroys and eliminates those who are unable to security

supply, energy and nutrients supply, adapt to environmental conditions such as temperature, etc., And will not be able to reproduce successfully. So only those that survive are those that can provide security, energy, and nutrients, adapt to environmental conditions, and reproduce successfully. Of course, traits that are useful in one environment may be harmful in another. In fact, superior traits are not selected. Rather, traits are selected that work in the best possible way in a specific environment for the benefit of realizing these fundamental principles. It can be said about these fundamental principles that; These fundamental principles are a guideline for natural selection to manage and program survival, adaptation, and evolution. In other words, the blind eye of natural selection is transformed into a clear eye by these fundamental principles. In fact, the design of natural selection is based on these fundamental principles. These are the fundamental principles of expressing natural selection for the act of choosing. There are other selections like sexual selection physics and chemistry choice and other selections. Whenever we talk about natural selection, these fundamental principles should be mentioned, along with natural selection. These principles are an integral part of natural selection.

When I say that, it must be said precisely that the selection was based on these fundamental principles because it must be stated what happened in nature. The fundamental principles give us a new approach to Darwin's theory of evolution and natural selection. From now on, before we ask whether traits are useful for survival or not? We have to ask if these traits are useful for providing energy and nutrients, for providing security, for adapting to environmental conditions, for reproduction, or not. Instead of saying what is the probability of survival, before that, we have to check what is the probability of providing energy and nutrients, the probability of providing security, and the probability of adapting to environmental conditions. Selection occurs at the level of genes, alleles, phenotypes, cellular organelles, cells, individuals, and populations based on fundamental principles. These fundamental principles should be highlighted in biology. These fundamental principles improve our understanding of nature and evolution. Selection pressure and selection forces are created by these fundamental principles. Selection pressure and selection forces may occur due to the provision of energy and nutrients, the provision of security, adaptation to environmental conditions, and the reproduction or transmission of genes to the next generation. In some cases, the reason for the evolution and adaptation of different species of organisms has been because each species can providing its fundamental principles differently.

If we leave aside the choice at the level of the laws of physics and chemistry, most of the choices will probably be based on fundamental principles only. Traits are inherited from one generation to another with small and random mutations that may change the performance of organisms in adapting to provide energy and nutrients (acquiring, finding, breaking down, and metabolizing energy and nutrients). This causes the population to undergo a process of natural selection based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply. In the science of ecology, the definition of ecology should be based on fundamental principles. The description of canvases shows what is really in nature, based on the fundamental principles. To be more precise; Ecology should be defined as providing energy and nutrients, providing security and adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, etc., and facilitating the reproduction or transfer of genes to the next generation. The evolution of the biosphere can be described by biological factors and available environmental resources, which are the same fundamental principles.

Important point: As I understood, the basic theories of psychologists such as Freud, Skinner, Abraham Maslow, and many other psychologists and psychological concepts such as sadness and joy, pain and suffering, depression, distress, theories of sociology and law and politics, and even human evolution and Anthropology, the evolution of the brain, the discovery of fire and many other concepts of human evolution, almost all human inventions, music, culture and ethics, the evolutionary cause of all these things is based on these fundamental principles and can be better described and explained. In future articles and books, I will further develop and argue some concepts and topics in biology and evolution based on these fundamental principles. For example, in the following articles, I will argue that the general features of extinction, survival, and finally speciation derive to a large extent from the

complex interaction of the mechanisms of fundamental principles. Still, scientific literature and scientific concepts based on these fundamental principles require a lot of work. I am waiting for your comments and criticisms to understand and complete this article.

Statement

"Funding: None"

Data accessibility

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declare no conflict of interest.

Reference

1,5, 29, 45,

DAWKINS, Richard (1976) The Selfish Gene. Oxford University Press
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Selfish_Gene.html?id=ekonDAAAQBAJ#v=onepage&q&f=false

2, 50, 51, 52,

Ernst W. Mayr (2002) What Evolution Is. Basic Books; Reprint edition (October 11, 2002)
What Evolution Is (Science Masters Series): Mayr, Ernst: 9780465044269: Amazon.com: Books
<https://www.amazon.com/What-Evolution-Science-Masters-Ernst/dp/0465044263>

3,8, 9, 19, 24, 27, 28, 32, 56, 57, 58,

Jane B. Reece, Lisa A. Urry, Michael L. Cain, Steven A. Wasserman, Peter V. Minorsky, Robert B. Jackson (2011) Campbell Biology. Publisher Pearson Education,
https://books.google.com/books/about/Campbell_Biology.html?id=1eosAAAAQBAJ

4

Gregory T. Ryan (2009) Understanding Natural Selection: Essential Concepts and Common Misconceptions | Evolution: Education and Outreach |

<https://evolution-outreach.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1007/s12052-009-0128-1>

6

ERIC R. PIANKA, Natural Selection of Optimal Reproductive Tactics, *American Zoologist*, Volume 16, Issue 4, November 1976, Pages 775–784,

<https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/16.4.775>

7

Charles A. S. Hall and Timothy McWhirter(2023) Maximum power in evolution, ecology and economics | *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2022.0290>

10

Robert L Lochmiller, Charlotte Deerenberg(2003) Trade-offs in evolutionary immunology: just what is the cost of immunity?, *Journal Oikos/onlinelibrary.wiley* .

<https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0706.2000.880110.x>

11

O. Seppälä, Natural selection on quantitative immune defence traits: a comparison between theory and data, *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*, Volume 28, Issue 1, 1 January 2015, Pages 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jeb.12528>

12,18, 59, 60

Darwin, Charles (1859) *Origin of Species*. John Murray

13

Christmas, M.J., Breed, M.F. & Lowe, A.J. (2016) Constraints to and conservation implications for climate change adaptation in plants. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-015-0782-5>

14

Vinogradova, O.L., Tomilovskaya, E.S. & Kozlovskaya, I.B. Gravity as a Factor in Evolutionary Adaptation of Animals to Living on the Earth. *Hum Physiol* **47**, 716–734 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0362119721070124>

15

Vargas, C., Argandoña, M., Reina-Bueno, M. et al. (2008) Unraveling the adaptation responses to osmotic and temperature stress in *Chromohalobacter salexigens*, a bacterium with broad salinity tolerance. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1746-1448-4-14>

16

Pradillon, F., Gaill, F. (2006). Pressure and life: some biological strategies. In: Amils, R., Ellis-Evans, C., Hinghofer-Szalkay, H. (eds) *Life in Extreme Environments*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-6285-8_21

17

Rob E Simmons, Res Altwegg(2010) Necks-for-sex or competing browsers? A critique of ideas on the evolution of giraffe, *Journal of Zoology*
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.2010.00711.x>

20,

Vinod K. Mony, Shawna Benjamin & Eyleen J. O'Rourke (2016) A lysosome-centered view of nutrient homeostasis, *Journal Autophagy*,
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15548627.2016.1147671>

21,

Jenna Lester, Joanne Lewsley, (2020)What are vesicles, and how do they work?
<https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/vesicle>

The site was visited on August 3, 2023

22, 25

Vacuole – Definition and Examples – Biology Online Dictionary

<https://www.biologyonline.com/dictionary/vacuole>

23

Gia K Voeltz, Melissa M Rolls, Tom A Rapoport (2002) Structural organization of the endoplasmic reticulum, *EMBO Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/embo-reports/kvf202>

26

Martin lowe(2011) Structural organization of the Golgi apparatus, *Current Opinion in Cell Biology*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceb.2010.10.004>

30

Hanna Appelqvist, Petra Wäster, Katarina Kågedal, Karin Öllinger (2013) The lysosome: from waste bag to potential therapeutic target, Journal of Molecular Cell Biology

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jmcb/mjt022>

31

Miroslav DUNDR; Tom MISTELI (2001) Functional architecture in the cell nucleus, Biochemical Journal

<https://doi.org/10.1042/bj3560297>

33

T.J Mitchison, L.P Cramer(1996)Actin-Based Cell Motility and Cell Locomotion. Cell Press journal

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0092-8674\(00\)81281-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0092-8674(00)81281-7)

34

Song Li,¹ Jun-Lin Guan,² and Shu Chien³(2005)Biochemistry and Biomechanics of Cell Motility. Annual Review of Biomedical Engineering. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.bioeng.7.060804.100340>

35

Daniel A Fletcher, Julie A Theriot(2004)An introduction to cell motility for the physical scientist. Physical Biology.

36

Chuong CM 1, Nickoloff BJ , Elias PM , Goldsmith LA , Macher E , Maderson PA , Sundberg JP , Tagami H , Plonka PM , Thestrup-Pederson K , Bernard BA , Schröder JM , Dotto P , Chang CM , Williams ML , Feingold KR , King LE , Kligman AM , Rees JL , Christophers E (2002)What is the 'true' function of skin?: Experimental Dermatology- Europe PMC

<https://europepmc.org/article/med/11994143#impact>

37

Albrecht von Haller A.V. Hill Jean-Martin Charcot Hugh Esmor Huxley Giovanni Alfonso Borelli (2023)Muscle | Systems, Types, Tissue, & Facts | Britannica

<https://www.britannica.com/science/muscle>

34

38

Robert A. Klocke ,Neil S. Cherniack, Ewald R. (2023) Human respiratory system | Description, Parts, Function, & Facts | Britannica

<https://www.britannica.com/science/human-respiratory-system>

39

Michael Francis Oliver, Bernard Edward Matthews, M. Elizabeth Rogers (2023) Circulatory system | Functions, Parts, & Facts | Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/science/circulatory-system>

40

Nicholas Carr Hightower, William Sircus, Harvey J. Dworken (2023)Human digestive system | Description, Parts, & Functions | Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/science/human-digestive-system>

41

Fenton Crosland Kelley, James Arthur Ramsay (2023, Excretion | Definition, Systems, Examples, Importance, & Facts | Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/science/excretion>

42

Solomon D. ErulkarThomas L. Lentz(2023)Nervous system | Definition, Function, Structure, & Facts | Britannica <https://www.britannica.com/science/nervous-system>

43

Gregory A. Wray (2015) Molecular clocks and the early evolution of metazoan nervous systems,

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2015.0046>

44

Cheng, Vivien and Cottrell, Paul and Johnson, John Mark and Sanal, Amrit, Endocrine System (October 18, 2018). Available at

SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3309237> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3309237>

46

Human reproductive system | Definition, Diagram & Facts | Britannica

<https://www.britannica.com/science/human-reproductive-system>

47

Martin Stevens (2013) *Sensory ecology, behaviour, and evolution*, Oxford University Press, USA,
[https://books.google.com/books?id= uJ4BJ77bZAC&lpg=PR4&pg=PR4#v=onepage&q&f=false](https://books.google.com/books?id=uJ4BJ77bZAC&lpg=PR4&pg=PR4#v=onepage&q&f=false)

48

Flammang, B., Suvarnaraksha, A., Markiewicz, J. et al. (2016) Tetrapod-like pelvic girdle in a walking cavefish, *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep23711>

49

Shubin, N., Tabin, C. & Carroll, S. Fossils, (1997) Genes and the evolution of animal limbs. *Nature* .
<https://doi.org/10.1038/41710>.

53

Arjen E van't Hof, Nicola Edmonds, Martina Dalíková, František Marec, Ilik J Saccheri(2011)Industrial Melanism in British Peppered Moths Has a Singular and Recent Mutational Origin, *Science Journal*
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1203043>

54

Cook, L., Saccheri, I. (2013) The peppered moth and industrial melanism: evolution of a natural selection case study. *Heredity*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.2012.92>

55

Geist, Valerius. "The Evolution of Horn-Like Organs." *Behaviour* 27, no. 3/4 (1966): 175–214.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/4533157>.

61

Kenneth R. Olson, Karl D. Straub (2015)The Role of Hydrogen Sulfide in Evolution and the Evolution of Hydrogen Sulfide in Metabolism and Signaling, *Physiology*
<https://doi.org/10.1152/physiol.00024.2015>

62

Pierre-Alain Monnard, David W Deamer (2002)Membrane self-assembly processes: Steps toward the first cellular life. *The Anatomical Record: An Official Publication of the American*
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ar.10154>

63

Richard C Lewontin (1970) The units of selection, *Annual review of ecology and systematics*
<https://www.annualreviews.org/content/journals/10.1146/annurev.es.01.110170.000245>

